

STUDY OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE STRUCTURE USING CT AND OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

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SUMMARY: Two main methods Computer Tomography (CT) and Optical Microscopy (OM), used for material study have the same output – an image of structure cut. Full structure information should be got from the image by a minimum of routine work. For textile composite standard image processing is not efficient, therefore, special processing based on specific structure features must be applied. Two complementary automated methods for low resolution CT images were developed. Their output mines all the information from images. It contains statistical structure parameters, yarn centre coordinates, textile layer position, yarn shape estimation, for instance. In the case of high resolution CT or OM, the yarn boundaries must be marked by the operator, but the information got from them is rich. Yarn cross section can be approximated by lens or ellipse; its longitudinal axis can be described effectively, etc. Used methods are explained in the paper and a lot of typical results in graphic form presented.

KEYWORDS: Textile reinforced composite, Real composite structure, Computer tomography, Optical Microscopy, Pattern recognition, Image processing

INTRODUCTION

Structure of woven reinforced composite has a strong effect to both the composite processing and final parameters of material. The deviations from the ideal structure considerably limit the composite quality and achievable parameters. Their values are worse than values of theoretical parameters predicted from ideal models. In order to better understand the nature of real composite processing, to improve the product quality, or to reliably predict real composite parameters, the actual 3D structure of representative volume should be known.

Two basic general methods for material 3D structure visualisation are used: Computer Tomography (CT) and Optical Microscopy (OM). Images of plane cut structures are the basic output of each from both the methods. However the application possibilities and quality of results are different. CT is non-destructive, fully automated method, the positions and parallelism of cuts are precise, but the resolution is low and the application is limited, for instance carbon-carbon composite cannot be used. On the other hand the optical microscopy exhibit very high resolution, it can be applied to any material, but it is a destructive method. Furthermore the precision of cut positions and parallelism is low. Getting of OM images requires a lot of hand work, only partial automation is possible.

From the above comparison the high resolution computer tomography appears as the most straightforward method for structure determination. At present time the 25 μm resolution is an industrial standard and 6 μm apparatus became laboratory equipment; see Ref. 1, for instance. Each apparatus has a sophisticated SW for X-ray diffraction processing. The result of non-destructive specimen testing is a set of photographs for exactly equidistant and parallel cuts of the structure. They are termed slices. Therefore, each slice is an image of the 2D structure cut.

In order to get any structure information, the boundaries of structure objects on 2D cuts must be known.

The task of getting object boundaries from images is not as simple as it appears from many reasons. In general, this task is a subject of image recognition or classification [2]. This very difficult discipline does not exhibit neither sophisticated procedures for general use at present time. From the practical point of view the main problem of automated recognition is that the contrast between different objects is low. The determination of boundaries is often a difficult task either for experienced operator. Furthermore, due to the relatively low CT resolution, the object details cannot be found. Therefore, standard image processing methods including commercial SW were not usually successful in automated and reliable object boundary finding.

Since OM images contain more details of the structure the object boundary determination is more complicated in comparison with CT. In this case the only procedure is to mark the boundaries by hand of skilled operator. This approach supposes time consuming, hard routine work.

From the structure point of view, on the other hand, the automated edge finding is the first step of structure image analysis. If the object boundaries are known, key structure information, for instance, yarn centre coordinate, yarn cross-section shape, yarn longitudinal axis etc., can be got from the sophisticated analysis of 2D images. If the object boundaries are found on all slices, the real 3D structure should be composed. The coordinates of object surfaces can be used for creation of 3D net for application of Finite Element Method (FEM) as well as these coordinates can be vertices of triangles for 3D object visualisation. The visualisation technique can use either low level Open GL or high level virtual reality systems and many other approaches.

Absolutely necessary and key operation on images is object boundary determination. The task is to automate this operation, but standard image processing is not a solution of this task. Nevertheless, there is a chance. Non-standard method that utilizes special image features should be used for automatic structure analysis. Therefore, depending on image type, this procedure can be fully or partially automated. A survey of effective method that allows finding a lot of structure parameters is presented in this paper. To our knowledge no similar work has been made in this area. In Ref. 3 the method of fractals is used for unusual and only partial structure description.

EXPERIMENT

Two composite samples used in the paper are noted A and B. Parameters of the samples are given in Table 1. Type A was produced on K. U. Leuven and AEA Technologies Tomahavk CT system was used for structure getting. This relatively low resolution CT system uses a spot size of approximately 25 μm . The data set contains 50 cross-sectional slices. Sample B was produced in the Institute of Mechanical Systems (IMES), Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich (ETHZ). The spot diameter was 6 and 12 μm . The data set has 278 slices.

Sample A was also processed by optical microscopy. The cuts were prepared by standard metallographic technology. The cut surface was scanned by image analysis system LUCIA M. Due to the extreme resolution of OM, only partial images were scanned. They were composed into cut final image by an original algorithm [4].

Table 1: Parameters of used samples

Sample/Image set ID	Pixel size	Material system	Number of layers	Volume fraction	Weave	Area density
A	27 μm	Glass/epoxy	25	42 %	Plain	420 g/m^2
B	B6	Glass/epoxy	19	51 %	Canvas	281 g/m^2
	B12					

Typical high resolution CT and extremely high resolution OM images are in Fig. 1. Only a small part of cut is in the OM image, its approximate area is marked in the CT image. Both longitudinal and perpendicular yarn cross sections are well visible on OM image, while on CT image the longitudinal yarns partially disappear. OM image resolution allows the individual fibers forming yarns to be well visible. Low resolution CT image is shown in Fig. 2a. Due to the low resolution, the longitudinal yarn cuts are almost invisible on CT, but the perpendicular yarn cross sections are well visible also in this low resolution image.

Fig. 1: Cut images. a) High resolution CT, b) Extremely high resolution OM

SPECIAL IMAGE PROCESSING

The use of standard or sophisticated methods of image analysis only leads to displaying and calculation of the area, where yarns are not present. Unfortunately, the result depends on the threshold used. The only practical result from this approach for this work is the determination of the correct threshold value that corresponds to yarn contents obtained by other method [3].

In order to get more structure information, special methods utilizing typical structure features need to be realised. Automation should be applied whenever possible. Automated image processing depends on its content that is given, first of all, by the resolution. Therefore, the special image processing will be described for three types of images, low resolution CT, high resolution CT, and extreme high resolution OM. Since full automation was possible only for low resolution CT, this method will be given in detail.

Automated Image Processing

This method uses specific, enhanced and important feature of images. It follows from Tab. 1 that the specimen consists of many layers. The layers are visible in CT images, like that in Fig. 2a, but better understanding the image can be made from 3D graph of image intensity shown in Fig. 2b. There are 2 areas of well defined mountains and valleys (one of them is on the right hand side of Fig. 2b), but also areas, where these two attributes are bad defined, exist. The mountains correspond to yarns while the valleys are gaps between neighboring yarns. Only an upper part of CT image is presented in Fig. 2b. The vertical line of CT image in Fig. 2a corresponds to the horizontal line in direction from left to right hand in 3D graph of Fig. 2b.

Fig. 2: Idea of low resolution CT image processing. a) Image, b) 3D graph of its intensity

Since both the boundaries between neighboring layers are well defined, the special processing starts with finding the positions of these layers or gaps between them from image intensity profile. In an ideal case intensity on CT image for any vertical line can be enough for this purpose. Due to the image and structure imperfections, see Fig. 2a, an average of horizontal lines is computed as a function of vertical position. Such a graph is shown in Fig. 3a. The maximums and minimums are well defined also for areas in original image, where they cannot be distinguished simply. Maximums can be used for determination of the position of layer center and minimums for the gap center coordinates.

Both the approaches, average intensity maximums and minimums, were used but in a little different way. First of all we focus to method of maximums. The mean intensity curves, like that in Fig. 3a drawn by thin pencil, are usually flat near all their extremes, but exceptional false extremes may exist. Two such false maximums are visible in Fig. 3a. In order to avoid such false extremes, the curve smoothing must be used. A lot of possibilities can be used for curve smoothing, for instance: moving average, polynomial regression, splines, Fourier series, because of curve quasi-periodicity, and others. Since data can exhibit a strong statistical component, the moving average was preferred. The smoothed curve is given by enhanced one in Fig. 3a. All the true maximums were searched by zeroes of negative slope from numeric derivative. Since the graphical derivative enhances errors, the derivative smoothing has to precede the zeroes finding.

Fig.3: Average intensity profiles for maximum method: a) in vertical direction, b) in horizontal direction for a selected layer

The same procedure can be applied to each layer. The row and columns are interchanged in the case of layer. The average intensity of columns for selected layer is shown by a thin curve in Fig. 3b as a function of row coordinate. Since the number of pixels in layer row is low, statistic nature of intensity is evident in Fig. 3b. However, the smoothing reveals correct maximums and their position can be found by the same algorithm as for layers above. In the realised program the algorithm for intensity profile was more complicated, only its basic idea is shown here for simplicity.

The method of minimums uses a different philosophy; its goal is to get almost the same level of intensity also for small image parts, e.g. yarn cross sections. Also the used approach for layer and yarn boundary determination is a little different. The actual intensity profile in vertical direction is shown in Fig. 4a. All the minimums are found by a simple numeric algorithm; however, the smoothing can be applied, if necessary. Because of quasi-periodicity of intensity profile, the Fourier series was used for smoothing in minimum method.

Fig.4: Average intensity profiles for minimum method: a) in vertical direction, b) in horizontal direction for a selected layer

As it can be expected, the layer intensity profile, shown in Fig. 4b, has a strong random component. The smoothing is necessary. However, the smoothed curve exhibits more minimums than necessary. In order to reduce false minimums the intensity curve was

approximated by the first and second order polynomials. They are shown in Fig. 4b, too. Only minimums under both the approximations are considered. Unfortunately, this approach does not remove all the false minimums; for instance, the second minimum in Fig. 4b was left. Since the distance of false minimum from its neighbours is smaller than average one, false minimum can be removed algorithmically.

By finding both the minimums in vertical direction and correct minimums for each layer the boundaries of layers and yarns can be found. Typical result is in Fig. 5a. The boundaries are marked by white colour. Practically at the first step the layers are found. Content of each layer is processed by standard image processing procedures as histogram equalisation, for instance. Then yarns in each layer are found and they are first processed by similar procedures as layers, then in the final step threshold and edge finding are applied. The correct level for threshold is used. Partial results are in Fig. 5b, from top to bottom: original image, gamma correction, filtering by mask of 5x5 and application of threshold with level of 70. In Fig. 5 there are final outputs of minimum method regarding both the layers and yarns. Numerical and graphical data contained in these images can be used for structure evaluation.

Fig.5: Layers and yarns: a) in image, b) results of yarn processing

Hand Image Processing

In the case of high resolution CT the automation gives only basic structure information. The contrast between neighbouring objects does not allow distinguish them one another and their edges cannot be found automatically. In this case the practical solution is to mark the boundaries by an experienced operator. Since defined colours can be used to distinguish the objects each other, the edge coordinate finding is a matter of simple program. Typical example of coloured edge marking is in Fig. 6a, cross sections of longitudinal yarns of very high resolution CT are marked by different colours.

The practical disadvantage of this approach is that the file size of grey scale image increases three times when colours are used. Therefore grey levels, white or dark, should be used for this purpose. Theoretically only a few levels near 0 and 255 levels can be used, since no image pixel can have this value, the image histogram must be stressed. Practically only dark

and white marks are allowed. In this case the object of some colour must be distinguished by a sophisticated algorithm. Such original program was realised. Example of the use of black colour to mark lens type cross sections of perpendicular yarns is in Fig. 6b.

Fig.6: Hand made marking of object edges: a) longitudinal yarns, b) perpendicular yarns

In the case of optical microscopy due to very complicated images no automation in object edge finding is possible at present time. Only object hand marking is possible. As consequence of very big size of image files, the use of colours is practically impossible due to the very long times for any computer response. The limitation to only the black and white marking is very strong. The hand processed images are similar to those in Fig. 6.

RESULTS

Depending on automated, semi-automated or hand CT or OM image processing, structure information of different level can be got from images of different resolution. Typical results got from methods presented in this paper will be summarised here. Automated method of maximums yields yarn center coordinates as its main output. They are shown by crosses for selected slices in Fig. 7 for both types of CT images. Careful inspection of images reveals that the agreement between computed and actual yarn center position is good for low resolution images. For high resolution, the center is shifted in several cases, especially in lower part. It is probably due to the presence of many black pixels. On the other hand, the algorithm finds correct centers in the upper part of this image, where the yarn boundaries are almost invisible.

Fig.7: Yarn centers: a) low resolution CT, b) high resolution CT

Two results of automated method of minimum are presented. The layer position in each slice of composite can be found and the graph of selected layer position in the composite sample (in the Z direction perpendicular to slices) is in Fig. 8a. The tendency of layer upward movement is clear from the points and linear regression. The shift is small, about 4 pixels. Linear approximation of position of all layers in composite is in Fig. 8b. Both shifts are possible, the final layer position is from about -7 to +5 pixels with respect to origin. The average shift is low, about 1 pixel.

Fig. 8: Layer shift in composite: a) actual shift and its linear approximation for selected layer, b) approximation for all layers

Either low resolution CT allows the estimation of yarn perpendicular cross section shapes using edges from yarn images in Fig. 5b bottom. The selected yarn cross section is in Fig. 9a and the transitions between yarns in Fig. 9b, where also the image processing of transition area between yarns, like that for yarns in Fig. 5b, is shown. The curves in Fig. 9 are distorted, the units on horizontal axis are about 10 time higher than those on vertical axis. In order to save computing time, the quadratic regression was used, although elliptic and lens approximation is possible. Relatively good results are shown in Fig. 9 to demonstrate program possibility. Most of results do not contain well defined yarns and transitions.

Fig. 9: Cross sections: a) yarn, b) transition processing, c) transition between yarns

Hand marking of object contours is used for very high resolution CT images as in Fig. 6. Thanks to a lot of points and higher range of coordinates, yarn cross sectional shape in perpendicular direction from Fig. 6b can be approximated effectively by lens or ellipse. Both the results are in Fig. 10. Again the shape distortion of rate about 1:10 exists; however, by

using 1:1 axes, almost nothing is visible. Both the approximations are acceptable and it is difficult to judge, which approximation is better.

Fig. 10: Yarn cross section approximation: a) lens, b) elliptic

The approximation of yarn longitudinal axis can be made from hand processed images like those in Fig. 6a. The Discrete Fourier Transform is used for its approximation. The details can be found elsewhere [5]. In the case of optical microscopy only the hand processed images are for disposal. The structure objects have a complicated shape and special object coordinate processing is necessary, see [5], for instance.

Especially for low resolution images; the data got by their processing have a strong statistical component. In many case the statistical application is the only method that can be applied, since the spread of graph points is too high to be reasonably approximated. Basic statistical parameters obtained from of low CT images are summarized in Tab. 2. All absolute values are in pixels. Both the maximum and minimum approaches lead to practically same results. The parameter accuracy is more than 10 %, the figure can be taken as typical for most of material structures. For completeness the minimum mean thickness is 9.9 pixels and maximum one is 21.2 pixels. The layer thickness varies in a wide range.

Tab. 2: Typical statistical parameters of composite structure

Structure parameter	Method of image processing	Average value	Standard deviation	Variation coefficient [%]
Layer thickness	maximum	15.8	2.2	14
Layer thickness	minimum	15.7	2.7	17
Yarn diameter	minimum	117	15	13

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The data acquisition from structure, in this case in the form of microphotographs, is a very complicated and expensive task, irrespective of device used. Therefore the task is to get all the information contained in images by a small amount of additional routine work. It means that fully automated image processing should be applied whenever possible. We have shown that low resolution CT images of textile composite can be processed by two complementary methods that use specific composite feature, a lot of parallel textile layers. Both methods use

mean image intensity profiles, but by a different manner and result in complementary information.

The yarn centre coordinates are the final result of maximum intensity method. The method is robust; the yarn centre can be found either in areas of low contrast, bad visible for human eye. Since the resolution is low variation of yarn position in composite cannot be mined from data, the coordinate can be evaluated only by standard numeric statistics. The automated minimum method, thanks to different philosophy yield more results. The method allows estimate yarn position tendency in composite, yarn shape and shape of transition area between adjacent yarns. The high resolution CT and OM itself results in much more structure information, but its mining from data is more complicated. The yarn perpendicular shape and its longitudinal axis can be got with high accuracy and good approximation.

Typical rule is valid. Low resolution images provide little information, but can be processed automatically, while high resolution microphotographs contain a lot of information but its mining is complicated difficult and time consuming. The decision for the use of method for structure study depends on the type of information that is expected. This paper may help in the decision.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Present work was supported by the grant No. 106/03/H150 from the Czech Science Foundation. Part of this work was made during the stay of Jan Vodolan in the Department MTM, K.U.Leuven. Jan Vodolan's stay in Leuven was funded by the Marie Curie Fellowship of the European Commission (HPMT-CT-2000-00030). The versatile support of Jan Vodolan's supervisor, Prof. S. Lomov from KU Leuven, is gratefully acknowledged. Authors are grateful to J. Shell from IMES, Zürich, for the permission to use her samples.

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